

Selected Teacher Competencies that Can Enhance CBC Implementation in Kenya

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Abstract

The introduction of a Competency-Based Curriculum in Kenya is replacing a knowledge-oriented and exam-centred curriculum that has defined the country's education system for close to four decades now. This new curriculum stresses skills development and learner-centredness as its most prominent distinguishing philosophy. However, the successful implementation of CBC is contingent upon the competencies of the teachers at the centre of its implementation. This paper sheds light on some of the fundamental competencies that can support teachers' capacities to deliver CBC as envisaged.

Keywords: *Competency Based Curriculum, competency, pedagogical competency, digital competency, leadership competency, personal and social competency, assessment competency.*

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Introduction

Introduced in 2017, CBC seeks to equip learners with 21st-century competencies and values. The competency-based curriculum, as conceived in Kenya, focuses on seven core competencies: critical thinking and problem-solving, creativity and imagination, self-efficacy, communication and collaboration, citizenship, learning to learn, and digital literacy (KICD, 2017). Unlike the 8-4-4 system, whose priority was syllabus coverage and examination, CBC's main focus is on the learner's holistic development, skills acquisition, and development through hands-on learning experiences and continuous assessment (Republic of Kenya, 2017). In CBC, learning is determined by the individual needs and potential of learners under a flexible context and parameters that regularly shift to match the learners' demands (Amutabi, 2021). As key components of CBC, critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity will enable graduates to solve everyday problems and flourish in the competitive, fast-paced global economy marked by shifting technological demands and advancements in the 21st century (Muchira et al., 2023).

Unlike the 8-4-4, CBC focuses less on exams. Instead, it prioritizes competency that is periodically assessed through customized formative assessments to measure both

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content mastery and practical abilities to improve learning. In Kenya, the rationale for CBC is to realign education to meet the evolving social, political, and economic needs that the previous curriculum could not address fully. Thus, it is expected that CBC will transform the exam-based system, which has hindered innovation, creativity, and context-specific problem-solving skills, to mitigate the unemployment monster tormenting the country's economy. Given its flexibility, CBC will yield its desired results if the country adjusts education structures across all levels to enable a seamless transition from one level to another.

The outgoing curriculum was mainly epitomized by the pressure and anxiety it caused among stakeholders, especially during national summative assessments. The ranking of schools according to performance and fear of failure resulted in unhealthy competition, leading to corruption and grand-scale exam cheating among stakeholders (Amutabi, 2021).

Amutabi (2021) is among the many scholars who believe that apart from being flexible, the new curriculum is friendly as it allows all types of learners to learn at their own pace without worrying about seat time. Additionally, under CBC, learning focuses on everyday skills and competency development, where learners are able to pursue their ambitions without conforming to the pressure and expectations of society (Amutabi, 2021). However, this claim is too idealistic, as societal needs and job market demands continue to shape educational outcomes.

To fulfil the goal of CBC, it calls for corresponding teacher competencies, whose roles have now shifted from repositories of knowledge to facilitators, learning coaches, and collaborators in knowledge creation. Teachers are key actors in any curriculum implementation. They provide practical insights into what works best in the classroom (Ndomondo et al., 2022). The teacher is the link between curriculum and instructional reality. Besides their role as instructional designers, teachers also play a significant role in selecting resources that support the curriculum. They select relevant textbooks, additional learning resources and teaching methods that match individual students' learning styles. According to Aldajah et al. (2014), students differ in the way they receive and process information due to their varying learning styles. Thus, it is the responsibility of the teacher to tailor learning resources and instructional methods to facilitate learning. Additionally, their constructive feedback is invaluable in monitoring and evaluation to help in curriculum improvement.

At the classroom level, CBC makes teachers facilitators of learning. Apart from interpreting complex concepts, they partner with students to create solutions to learning problems. Their understanding that students are not tabula rasa (Ndomondo et al., 2022) enables them to exercise leadership by creating an environment that favours the active participation of learners. The CBC is a curriculum that stresses teachers' competencies as enablers of effective learning. Thus, for CBC to benefit the learner, society, and nation, the teacher must demonstrate significant mastery of the subject matter and the ability to manage teaching and learning effectively. Only a competent teacher can lead learners to the acquisition and development of competencies.

What are Teacher Competencies?

Competencies are the distinct abilities that a teacher needs to help learners acquire knowledge, skills, attitudes and values. The knowledge, skills, and capabilities of

teachers are central aspects that differentiate one educator from another. Good teachers exhibit a multidimensional approach to their roles, embodying teaching, counselling, supervision, and student evaluation (Wordu & Isiah, 2021). It is repeatedly affirmed that the quality of a nation is dependent upon the quality of its citizens. This, in turn, hinges on the quality of education they receive, which is fundamentally determined by the calibre of their teachers (Wordu & Isiah, 2021).

Having realized the significant role played by teachers in their education process, many countries have boosted efforts with a view of upskilling their teaching workforce. Often considered the child's 'In loco parentis', their immediate God, because of being role models to school children, the importance of teachers cannot be overstated (Wordu & Isiah, 2021).

As the world steadily shifts to connectivism, constructivism, and cognitivism, the role of the teachers also changes. As such, the teaching and learning process is no longer autocratic but a democratic one where learners' participation is indispensable (Wordu & Isiah, 2021).

To ensure that new teachers are effectively integrated into the unfamiliar educational territories, they must be equipped with fundamental pedagogical knowledge, skills, competencies, and values. This preparation is critical in forming a strong professional foundation. Instead of adopting an authoritarian role or serving merely as repositories of knowledge from which students absorb passively, the important competency required of new educators should be the ability to facilitate an engaging and interactive learning process (Wordu & Isiah, 2021).

Teacher Competencies for Successful CBC Implementation in Kenya

The shift to CBC needs teachers with competencies that transcend conventional knowledge transfer. This section reviews some selected competencies that can enhance CBC implementation, focusing on pedagogical, leadership, assessment, personal, social, and digital literacy competencies.

Pedagogical Competencies

Pedagogical competence refers to teachers' ability to manage learning effectively. This includes planning a learning program, interacting during the learning process, and conducting assessments (Akhyak et al., 2013). It is the possession of the knowledge and skills necessary for effective teaching. Teachers require a deep understanding of the Competency-Based Curriculum learning areas, the combination of theory and research, and the thoughtful application of this knowledge would boost learning outcomes. CBC implementers, therefore, need to utilize the resources within their reach to make learning as productive as possible. To others, the idea of pedagogical competence is often understood as the minimum professional standard, typically defined by law, that individuals must meet to effectively perform their roles in the teaching profession (Suciu, 2011). However, this may only partially fulfil the objectives of Kenya's Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC). The CBC emphasizes cultivating critical thinking, creativity, and adaptability in learners, meaning that teachers must go beyond basic competencies. To efficiently support these goals, educators need to participate in continuous professional development and promote inclusivity and diversity in their classrooms. So, redefining pedagogical competence to include these

innovative skills and the ability to create learner-centred classrooms is exceedingly important for the successful implementation of the CBC in Kenya.

Purnama et al. (2021), say pedagogical competence represents a critical facet of the competencies that educators must master to ensure effective teaching practices. This concept covers the educational and instructional qualifications vital for teachers. Among these qualifications, a fundamental requirement is the ability to effectively manage and facilitate the teaching and learning process within the classroom environment. Such competencies are integral to creating an engaging and productive educational experience for students. The concept of pedagogical competence is undeniably important for effective teaching, particularly in the context of Kenya's Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC), which stresses the development of practical skills and holistic learner engagement. However, in light of the CBC, this competence must also include the adoption of innovative, learner-centred approaches that encourage critical thinking, collaboration, and cultural relevance. Thus, enhancing pedagogical competence is not limited to managing the classroom effectively but also about equipping learners with the skills necessary to solve real problems in an ever-changing society. For example, one of the learning areas in Kenya's CBC is Science and Technology in Junior school. The subject builds on the competencies introduced at the lower primary level under the subject of Environmental Activities. Inquiry-based learning approaches should be employed throughout the learning experiences in this area, as advocated by John Dewey's social constructivist theory, which emphasizes that the learner should be offered an opportunity to learn through participation in hands-on activities (KICD, 2017). This pedagogical competence is particularly preferred as it exposes learners to experiences that provoke them to question, collaborate, think critically, conduct research, solve problems, communicate and discover new knowledge (KICD, 2017). This view is consistent with Gholam (2019), who states that inquiry-based learning (IBL) is a student-centred approach that is guided by students' questions and inborn curiosity.

Digital Literacy Competence

An educator or teacher must exhibit satisfactory capability to use digital technology and communication tools to access, use, and even evaluate digital-based learning (Marnita et al., 2023). This competence is what teachers need to develop an effective and efficient teaching and learning process. Teachers' digital literacy competencies help create student enthusiasm and rapport between teachers and students in the class on thematic lessons, especially science, which is usually considered difficult by students (Marnita et al., 2023).

Digital literacy is a crucial competency for CBC educators. By incorporating ICT in teaching and learning, quality, equity, and efficiency are attained (OECD, 2023). For Murithi and Yoo (2021), ICT is a means of creating access to education, especially in marginalised populations, by making teaching and learning enjoyable and creating a more inclusive education system. According to the OECD (2023) report, a vital education in the 21st century is characterised by teachers and students with the wherewithal to utilise digital tools and resources to augment learning. Digital technologies are lauded for providing new opportunities for collaboration, interaction, communication, and the seamless exchange of ideas and knowledge. Lately, some of digital tools being used in the field of education include mobile devices, social media, blogs, and podcasting. Such technologies have been seen to affect student learning and attitudes towards learning in myriad ways (Carrie Taylor & Timothy Hinchman, 2020). For this reason, countries are now incentivising teachers to ease access to digital

training to acquire pedagogical competencies. Despite the scarcity of resources, which continues to hinder many countries from digitising their education systems, some have made deliberate efforts to establish digital competency literacy standards that are prerequisites for preservice teachers. It is not uncommon to hear of regular mandatory in-service teacher training and the provision of professional learning resources (OECD, 2023).

Kenya's 8-4-4 classroom teaching lacked an immediate learning environment, faster assessment, and greater engagement. In contrast, emerging digital learning tools and technology seal this gap (Dancsa et al., 2023). For instance, as smartphones become increasingly ubiquitous, it is only sound that teachers use them to reinforce their instruction in the classroom. This is, however, hindered by the fact that Kenya's basic education does not allow learners to carry phones to school. It is considered a grave mistake to own any phone within the school. There have been cases where students are banned from school for possessing mobile phones. Now, it becomes a challenge for the teacher to use their only phone for the benefit of a crowded classroom.

Digital Tools

Digital tools refer to any software, app, technology, extensions, add-ons, or websites that can be accessed via an internet connection and improve the capacity of a teacher to make learning effective. The integration of learners with digital tools allows them to play a more active role in their learning process (Dancsa et al., 2023). If digital tools are utilized in CBC, the teacher will play a leading role in the learning process by validating learning effectiveness. With the availability of digital resources, learners can download the information they need or upload their content (Dancsa et al., 2023)).

a) Flipgrid

Flipgrid provides an ample avenue for students to frequently interact socially with one another and actively engage with the course material as they would in a physically walled classroom (Carrie Taylor & Timothy Hinchman, 2020). As explained by Carrie Taylor and Timothy Hinchman (2020), as a video response technology, Flipgrid can support experiential learning and enables educators to engage students in a variety of learning and assessment activities. One of the most important features of Flipgrid is its free availability to use on all platforms: IOS, Android, and Web (Carrie Taylor & Timothy Hinchman, 2020). Flipgrid can be useful for topic introduction, group discussions and assessment.

b) Facebook

Facebook is presently one of the most popular social networking sites (Means, 2019). Previous research has shown both advantages and disadvantages of using Facebook as a tool to support curriculum (Tscholl et al., 2023). Facebook can serve as a Learning Management System in the educational environment and support a community of learners (Means, 2019).

c) Edmodo

Edmodo is an educational website that takes the ideas of a social network, refines them, and makes them suitable for a classroom. Through Edmodo, students and teachers can connect and share ideas, problems, and helpful tips. For example, a teacher can assign and grade assignments remotely on Edmodo; students can get help from the entire class on Edmodo. There is no bullying or inappropriate content because the teacher can see everything posted on Edmodo. Parents can also join the class to bring transparency that is only possible with technology. Overall, Edmodo is

a great companion to just any class. For instance, a study by Hoesny et al. (2020) found that Edmodo could facilitate English class community building and foster communication and collaboration between teachers and students. It encourages collaborative work and digital content creation, enhancing students' technology skills.

Personal and Social Competencies

The emotional and social competencies have been touted for enabling teachers to create effective relationships, manage emotional situations, and create a favourable learning environment within the school (Molina-Moreno et al., 2024). The scarcity of these competencies can result in emotional exhaustion and negatively impact the classroom environment. These competencies, therefore, need to be reinforced to adapt teachers to the evolving needs of the education domain.

Personal competencies are related to the personal behaviour of teachers who must have noble values so that are reflected in their daily activities (Amsal et al., 2022). Personal competence is not part of the curriculum that teachers have to teach their students, but it is a strength that every teacher must exhibit to lead students to become good citizens as envisioned in CBC's Citizenship Competence.

Educators nourish an atmosphere in which each child has a positive, cultivating relationship with caring adults by maintaining a positive and nurturing learning environment (Mandal, n.d.).

Social competence refers to the capacity of teachers as part of the community to communicate and relate well with learners, fellow educators, education personnel, parents/ guardians of learners, and the surrounding neighbourhood (Amsal et al., 2022).

The teacher's social competence is an attitude of willingness and willingness to provide community service through his professional work to achieve the goal of education. Social competence is related to the ability of the teacher to be a social being in relation to others, who are expected to be able to work together, have politeness in their role, communicate, and have empathy towards others. The teacher's social competence, as part of the school organization, should carry out a series of tasks in accordance with the functions to be performed.

Leadership Competency

Leadership is a critical strength that all teachers should demonstrate. A teacher should be able to assume leadership roles and responsibilities in and outside the classroom environment. As a leader in the learning process, he/she should support learners in acquiring the desired competencies to fulfil the established national performance standards and empower learners to solve immediate problems using the competencies attained in school. Teachers lead on all fronts, from problem identification to solution creation and implementation. They are the agents of change and innovation in learning institutions—they are not fence-sitters. Teachers should take up leadership roles whenever necessary, regardless of whether they are formally assigned, to salvage the interests of the learner, who is the centre of the Competency-Based Curriculum. They can drastically revolutionize the teaching profession by tremendously advancing it, hence realizing job satisfaction. As Kenya embraces the CBC, teachers must demonstrate a willingness to lead learners, colleagues, and parents toward a future where education is an avenue for competence acquisition and development.

Assessment Competency

Assessment competency encompasses flexibility, integrity, and accuracy in reporting the learner's proficiency in an area. If a teacher conducts a just, transparent, unbiased assessment, gaps for improvement can be identified for timely interventions. Regarding CBC, assessment is the measurement that provides insight into what the student has grasped, needs to learn and has learnt and where improvement is needed (Opondo & Afwande, 2023). Therefore, regular assessment and feedback about the learner's academics is the foundation for CBC.

Competencies in the CBC are meant to be assessed through formative assessment, which necessitates a paradigm shift from the conventional teacher-centred assessment to student-centred assessment techniques (Wafubwa, 2021). Formative assessment ensures the learner acquires and applies the desired competencies in practical scenarios. This is the remedy to the 8-4-4's emphasis on end-term exams and national summative assessments as the only screens for learning. A competency-based Curriculum emphasizes continuous formative assessment, which helps track a student's progress over time (KICD, 2017). Reports from these assessments are essential in evaluating knowledge, skills, values, and creativity to form a basis for learning-based decision-making and ensure continuity in learning.

The teacher should be well versed in the use of various assessment tools such as individualized observation, oral/nonverbal questioning, assessment portfolio, checklist, and rating scale to establish the current level of performance or entry behaviour and tailor support to each learner (Opondo & Afwande, 2023). For instance, portfolio assessment allows students to showcase their strengths and weaknesses (Fina & A, 1992). Additionally, portfolios bring together the learner, parent/guardian, teacher and school administration to reflect on the learner's progress. A portfolio can also trigger children to reflect on their performance and readjust to improve where their performance is unsatisfactory. It is also a sure way of maintaining the child at the centre of a curriculum.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the success of a Competency-Based Curriculum in Kenya hinges on the competency of the teachers delivering it. Teachers must be equipped with select competencies like pedagogical competency, leadership competency, digital competency, assessment competency, and personal and leadership competency. These competencies are essential as they are in harmony with learner competencies such as critical thinking and problem-solving, creativity and imagination, self-efficacy, communication and collaboration, citizenship, learning to learn, and digital literacy.

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